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CONTENTS

1-Sho'ba. Zamonaviy psixologiyaning nazariy-metodologik asoslari va muammolari.....	15
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA PSIXOLOGIK XIZMAT: DAVLAT SIYOSATI, AMALIY MEXANIZMLARI VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH YO'LI	16
Hilola Umarova	
ZAMONAVIY PSIXOLOGIYANING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI VA SOG'LOM PSIXOLOGIK MUHITNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI.....	19
Karimova E'zozxon Gapirjonovna	
RAHBAR XODIMLARGA PSIXOLOGIK XIZMAT KO'RSATISHNING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK MEXANIZMLARI	23
Qo'ng'irotboy Avezimbetovich Sharipov	
"DIGITAL TWIN" TEXNOLOGIYASI VA INNOVATSION BOSHQARUV PARADIGMASI	26
Raxmanov Zafar Yashinovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ПСИХОЛОГИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ И ПУТИ ИХ РЕШЕНИЯ.....	28
Гайрат Бахрамович Шаумаров	
MACHINE PSYCHOLOGY: BRIDGING HUMAN LEARNING PRINCIPLES AND ARTIFICIAL GENERAL INTELLIGENCE DEVELOPMENT	31
Farkhod Alisherovich Alisherov, Nigora Ruzikulova Shukhratovna	
MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA INKLYUZIVLIK SIYOSATINI AMALGA OSHIRISHDA RAHBARLIK FAOLIYATINING PSIXOLOGIK VA TASHKILIY ASOSLARI	39
Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna	
TALABALARNING ILMIY INNOVATSION FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	44
Abdullayeva Barno Sayfuddinovna	
ONANING O'ZI HAQIDAGI TASAVVURLARINING FARZAND MUNOSABATIGA ALOQADORLIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	49
Abdullayeva Dilbar Ubaydullayevna	
AVLODLAR KONTEKSTIDA MOLIYAVIY XULQ-ATVOR: PUL PSIXOLOGIYASINING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK TAHLILI	53
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna	
EMOTIONAL BURNOUT AND STRESS AS PSYCHOLOGICAL RISKS OF A NOTARY'S PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY	56
Arystanbek Aiymszhan, Aitysheva Aigul Mukataevna	
UYUSHMAGAN YOSHLARNING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK MOSLASHGANLIGINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	59
Atabayeva Nargis Batirovna	
MUAMMOLI PEDAGOGIK VAZIYATLARGA O'QITUVCHI QAROR QABUL QILISHINING DIFFERENSIAL XUSUSIYATLARI	61
P.S.Ergashev	
SPORT BOSHQARUVI SOHASIDAGI DAVLAT FUQAROLIK XIZMATCHILARIDA OILAVIY VA KASBIY TOLERANTLIK.....	64
O.E. Hayitov	
O'QUVCHILARDA KOGNITIV JARAYONLARINING RIVOJLANISHI INTELLEKT SHAKLLANISHINING MUHIM OMILI SIFATIDA.....	67
Ashurov Ramzidin Ramazonovich	

INKLYUZIV PSIXOLOGIYA KONSEPSIYASI: IMKONIYATI CHEKLANGAN SHAXSLARNING PSIXOLOGIK RIVOJLANISHINI O'RGANISHDA ZAMONAVIY METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLAR.....	70
Abdullayeva Yulduz Muftillo qizi	
OILAVIY MUNOSABATLAR TRANSFORMATSIYASI JARAYONLARIDA YOSH OILA VAKILLARI XULQIDAGI AYRIM MUAMMOLAR.....	72
V.M. KARIMOVA	
UMUMIY O'RTA TA'LIM TIZIMIDAGI PSIXOLOGIK XIZMATNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ZARURATI MASALALARI	75
Akramova Feruza Akmalovna	
TALABALARDA ALTRUIZM NAMOYON BO'LISHIGA SHAXS XUSUSIYATLARINING TA'SIRI	77
Kamolova Nilufar Davir qizi	
PEDAGOGLARDA KASBIY STRESS VA UNING OQIBATLARI	82
Karshiyeva Dilafuz Suyunovna	
SINERGETIK TAFAKKUR — ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM JARAYONINING INNOVATSION YO'NALISHI.....	84
Masharipova Farog'at Matrasulovna	
OILADA MA'NAVIY, AXLOQIY VA MADANIY MALAKALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK JIHATLARI	88
Mirabdullayeva Shoiraxon Abdulkayevna	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI IMIJINI BELGILOVCHI ASOSIY BIXEVIORISTIK KOMPONENTNING ILMIY-NAZARIY TAHLILI	91
Mirashirova Nargiza Anvarovna	
SPORTCHILAR PSIXOFIZIOLOGIK HOLATINI BAHOLASHDA TEPPIG-TEST METODIKASI	94
S.U.Nazarov	
ILK O'SPIRINLARDA HAVAS KASB TANLASH MOTIVI SIFATIDA.....	98
Nishanova Zamira Taskayevna	
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В ПСИХОТЕРАПЕВТИЧЕСКОЙ ПРАКТИКЕ.....	101
Останов Шухрат Шарифович	
TALABALAR O'ZINI O'ZI FAOLLASHTIRISHI MUAMMOSINING MAHALLIY MUHITDA TADQIQ ETILISHI.....	106
Qurbonboyev Azimbek Nazirboy o'g'li	
VOYAGA YETMAGANLAR O'RTASIDA NAZORATSIZLIK VA HUQUQBUZARLIKLAR PROFILAKTIKASI MASALALARI	109
Qodirov Obid Safarovich, Raxmatov Faxriddin Umarovich	
PSIXOLOGLARNING PROFESSIONAL TAFAKKURI.....	114
Ra'no Ismaylova	
O'ZBEKISTON VA JAHON MAMLAKATLARIDAGI OILAVIY AJRALISHLARNING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARIDAGI O'ZIGA XOSLIKLARNING EMPIRIK TAHLILI	118
Ro'ziqulov Faxriddin Rasulovich	
SHAXS NAZARIYASIGA MAHALLIY PSIXOLOGLAR TOMONIDAN KOGNITIV YONDASHUV	121
Tursunov Lutfulla Sayfullayevich	
BO'LAJAK MUTAXASSISLARINING KASBIY RIVOJLANISHIGA QARATILGAN ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR TAXLILI.....	123
Tuychiyeva Saodat Melikuziyevna	
TA'LIM MENEJMENTIDA SHAXSLARARO MUNOSABATLAR - MUVAFFAQIYATLI BOSHQARUVNING ASOSIY OMILI SIFATIDA	126
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Jalolova Nafisa O'ktam qizi	
TALABALARDA RUHIY SALOMATLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASHDA STRESSGA BARDOSHLILIK VA EMOTSIONAL INTELLEKTNING ROLI.....	128
Xajiyeva Iroda Adambayevna	

ZAMONAVIY GLOBAL MUAMMOLARDA ALTRUIZMNING ROLI	131
Xatamova Ferangiz Ibodullojevna	
QUROLLI TO‘QNASHUVLARDAN OLIB KELINGAN BOLALARNI PSIXOLOGIK REABILITATSIYA QILISH MUAMMOLARI	134
S.R.Yuldashev	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ МЫСЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ ОПЕРАЦИЙ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА	137
Алимова Гулчехра Кабелевна	
О‘QUVCHILARDA MUVAFFAQIYAT MOTIVATSIYASINI KUCHAYTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI	139
Karimov Sherzod Abdurasulovich	
HARBIY XIZMATCHILAR OILALARIDAGI INQIROZLARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI	142
Sh.S.Kurbanova	
AUDITORLIK QOBILIYATI RAHBAR KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIGI KO‘RSATKICHI SIFATIDA	145
Xolmurodova Dilnoza Xolmurodovna	
САМОРЕГУЛЯЦИЯ У СТУДЕНТОВ КАК ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ ФЕНОМЕН.....	149
Махмудова Д.А., Махманова К. Д.	
СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ОБЩЕСТВЕ.....	151
Султанова Амина Анваровна, Дjon Муминова Дильфуза	
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ БЛАГОПОЛУЧИЕ СТУДЕНТОВ С РАЗНЫМ УРОВНЕМ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ НАПРАВЛЕННОСТИ	154
Тиллашайхова Хосият Азаматовна	
2-Sho‘ba. Zamonaviy shaxs rivojlanishining ijtimoiy-psixologi muammolari	159
ВЛИЯНИЕ ИНТЕНСИВНОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ГАДЖЕТОВ НА ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЗАЩИТ У ПОДРОСТКОВ	160
Е.Г.Алимова	
ZAMONAVIY SHAXS RIVOJLANISHIDA OMMAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARINING TA’SIRI	163
Abdinazarova Bibixonim Rashid qizi	
INKLYUZIV TA’LIM TIZIMIDA O‘QUVCHILARNING PSIXOLOGIK MOSLASHUV JARAYONINI QO‘LLAB-QUVVATLASH: SAMARALI PEDAGOGIK VA PSIXOLOGIK YONDASHUVLAR	166
Abdullayeva Yulduz Muftillo qizi, Giyazova Zuhro Sattorovna	
ZAMONAVIY BOSHQARUV TIZIMLARIDA QAROR QABUL QILISH SAMARADORLIGI	169
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Artikov Samandar Arzikulovich	
IJTIMOY PSIXOLOGIK TADQIQOTLARDA OILA VA OILAVIY QADRIYATLARNING O‘RGANILGANLIK HOLATI	172
Abibullaeva Perdegul Ongarbaevna	
OILAVIY JANJALLAR NATIJASIDA YUZAGA KELUVCHI STRESS VA DEPRESSIV HOLATLARNING PSIXODIAGNOSTIKASI.....	174
Boboyeva Feruza Azimjonovna	
ZAMONAVIY O‘SMIR SHAXSINING EMOTSIONAL INTELLEKTI RIVOJLANISHIDA IJTIMOY OMILLARNING ROLI.....	178
Ergashev Dilshod Tirkash o‘g‘li	
PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF DIGITAL INFORMATION USE THAT CONTRIBUTE TO THE EROSION OF SOCIAL NORMS IN THE MINDS OF YOUNG PEOPLE	180
Ganiev Maksudjon Najimovich	
ZAMONAVIY SHAXS RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMOLARI	184
Gulnafar Abdullayeva	

RUHIY SALOMATLIKNI SAQLASHDA PSIXOLOGIK OMILLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	187
Hasanova Dilshoda Avazbek qizi	
EMOTSIONAL INTELLEKT - ZAMONAVIY SHAXS RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOY – PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMOSI SIFATIDA.....	190
Ismailova Nilufar Baxadirovna	
OILALARDA INTERNETGA TOBELIKNING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI HOLATI.....	193
Kushakova Nargiza Islambayevna, Ergasheva Sarvinoz Shavqiddin qizi	
AKADEMIK PROKRASTINATSIYANI O’RGANISH BO’YICHA XORIJIY OLIMLAR TAHLILI	196
Mardiyeva Shaxnoza Amirovna	
STEAM TA’LIM VOSITASIDA O’QUVCHILARNING KREATIV QOBILIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	199
Matkarimova Nilufar	
MAKTABGACHA YOSHDA BOLANING MUVAFFAQIYATLI IJTIMOYLAHVUVI MEZONLARI	203
Norbosheva Maqsuda Achilovna	
DEVIANT XULQ-ATVORLI O’SMIY QIZLARDA HIMOYA MEXANIZMLARINING IJTIMOYLAHVUVA TA’SIRI	206
Parpiyeva Shaxnoza	
PSIXOLOGIYADA O’ZINI O’ZI FAOLLASHTIRISH FENOMENIGA NISBATAN ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	209
Qurbonboyev Azimbek Nazirboy o’g’li, Istamburiyev Muhammadali Abdulazizovich	
VELOSIPIED SPORT TURI BILAN SHUG’ULLANUVCHILARNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	212
Raxmonova Go’zal Bobir qizi	
SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CONSEQUENCES OF CYBERBULLYING ON ADOLESCENTS’ INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION	215
Salomov Shamsiddin Sabokhiddin ugli	
RUHIY SALOMATLIKNI QO’LLAB-QUVVATLASH ORQALI BO’LAJAK LOGOPEDLARNING INKLYUZIV FAOLIYATGA PSIXOLOGIK TAYYORGARLIGINI OSHIRISH	219
Sharifova Maxliyo Zarif qizi	
TALABALARDA TA’LIM JARAYONIGA MOSLASHISHNING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	222
Ubaydullayev Nuriddin Toxir o’g’li	
PEDAGOGIK JAMOALARDA PROJECT MANAGEMENT METODLARINING JAMOAVIY MOTIVATSIYAGA TA’SIRI.....	225
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Ashurov Muhammad Zokir o’g’li	
AYOLLARDA KASB VA OILA MUVOZANATINI TA’MINLASHNING PSIXOLOGIK OMILLARI	227
Zuxra Mansurxonova	
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ СПОСОБЫ ВЫЯВЛЕНИЯ КРИМИНАЛЬНОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ В ПОДРОСТКОВОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ	230
Пардаева Умида Мухтар қизи	
PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LIFE POSITION OF UNORGANIZED YOUTH.....	234
Atabayeva Nargis Batirovna, Alimjonova Durдона Yunusjon qizi	
YOSHLARNI OTA-ONALIK MAS’ULIYATIGA TAYYORLASH - PSIXOLOGIYANING DOLZARB MUAMMOSI SIFATIDA.....	238
Bilolova Zamira Baxtiyarovna	
OTA-ONA VA FARZAND MUNOSABATLARINI TADQIQ ETISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI.....	241
D.U.Abdullayeva, I.X.Panjiyeva	
SHAXS IJTIMOY MOSLASHUVIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI PSIXOLOGIK OMILLARNING O’ZIGA XOSLIGI	244
Dusboev Asliddin Turgunovich	
PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FOUNDATIONS OF SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE AND ITS STRUCTURAL COMPONENTS.....	247
G.A.Valiyeva	

YOSH OILALARNING MUSTAHKAMLIGIGA ZAMONAVIY AXBOROT VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING TA’SIRI.....	250
Kushakova Nargiza Islambaevna	
TALABALARDA IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK KOMPETENTLIK SHAKLLANISHINING DINAMIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	253
Nazarova Malohat Axmedovna	
SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CONSEQUENCES OF CYBERBULLYING ON ADOLESCENTS’ INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION	255
Salomov Shamsiddin Sabokhiddin ugli	
OTA-ONA VA FARZAND MUNOSABATLARINI BARQARORLASHTIRISHDA AFILIATSIYA MOTIVINING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI	259
Samatova Sevara G’ayratovna	
GENDER STEREOTIPLARI - QABUL QILINGAN ME’YOR VA QOIDALARGA XULQ-ATVORINI MOSLASHTIRISH.....	263
Saribayeva Umida Sattarovna	
DINIY MUTAASSIBLIK, EKSTREMIZM VA TERRORCHILIKNING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	266
Sobirov Jamoliddin, Nazarov A.S.	
O’QUVCHI YOSHLARNING O’ZARO MUNOSABATLARIDA TEAM BUILDING TA’SIRI VA AHAMIYATI.....	267
Turayev Nurmuhammad Alibek	
O’SMIRLARDA DEVIANT XULQNING KONATIV ASPEKTLARI BO’YICHA PSIXODIAGNOSTIK TAHLIL (HUDUDIIY VA GENDER FARQLARI MISOLIDA)	269
Turayeva Gulchehra Urayimovna	
TALABALAR IJTIMOY FAOLLIGINI OSHIRISHNING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK JIHATLARI	273
Umarov Saidnemat Burxanovich	
O’SMIRLIK DAVRIDA DEVIANT XULQ-ATVOR NAMOYON BO’LISHINING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	275
Umarova Navbahor Shakirovna, Xalilova Sarvinoz Qodirali qizi	
TA’LIM MUASSASALARIDA BOSHQARISHDA KOGNITIV MENEJMENT YANGI MODEL SIFATIDA	278
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Sadinova Marjona Akmal qizi	
SPORTCHILAR OILASIDAGI SIBLINGLAR MUNOSABATLARINING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	281
G.H.Usmonova	
YOSHLAR PSIXOLOGIK MADANIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA QADRIYATLAR TIZIMI VA IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK MEKANIZMLARNING O’ZARO TA’SIRI: NAZARIY ASOSLAR VA EMPIRIK TAHLIL.....	283
X.A. Bobanov	
KIBERIJTIMOYLAHVU IJTIMOY PSIXOLOGIK HODISA SIFATIDA.....	287
Yuldashev S.R., Muhiddinova M.N	
MILLIY VA DINIY URF-ODAT VA AN’ANALARDA AXLOQ NORMALARINING MUJASSAMLASHGANLIGI.....	289
D.Sh.Yuldashova, Miraliyeva Zulayxo Abdurauf qizi, Xidirova Gulhayo Muhiddin qizi	
РАЗВИТИЕ КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ НАВЫКОВ У СТУДЕНТОВ-ПСИХОЛОГОВ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ОБЩЕСТВЕ	292
Аскарова Гулрух, Ашурова Анастасия	
КОММУНИКАТИВНАЯ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТЬ КАК ФАКТОР ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО СТАНОВЛЕНИЯ ПЕДАГОГА-ПСИХОЛОГА	296
Аскарова Гулрух, Рахимова Робиябону	
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ОБРАЗА «Я» У ПОДРОСТКОВ.....	300
Махмудова Диларом Ахмадовна, Сафаев Музаффар Зафар угли	
СЕМЕЙНАЯ СИНЕРГИЯ КАК ФАКТОР РАЗВИТИЯ “Я-КОНЦЕПЦИИ” В ПОДРОСТКОВОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ	303
Одилова Наира Гулямовна	

3-Sho'ba. Yosh va pedagogik psixologiya: ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonidagi muammolar	307
TALIM MUASSASALARIDA PSIXOLOGIK KONTRAKTNI MUSTAHKAMLASH UCHUN TASHKILIY-PSIXOLOGIK INTERVENSIYALAR	308
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Bayzaqova Madina Ibragimovna	
TALIM OLISH JARAYONIDA STRESSGA BARQARORLIK NAMOYON BO'LISHINING YOSH PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI	312
N.Z.Ismoilova, M.K.Ismoilova	
BOLALARDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING PSIXOLOGIK TA'SIRI	315
Aliyeva Kamola Saidnegmatovna, Tulqunova Barnooy Behzodjon qizi	
PEDAGOGLARDA KASBIY STRESSNING NAMOYON BO'LISH XUSUSIYATLARI	317
Boymirzayeva Nafisaxon Baxodir qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA STEAM TALIM TEXNOLOGIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI	321
G.M.Qurbonova	
PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF DIGITAL INFORMATION USE THAT CONTRIBUTE TO THE EROSION OF SOCIAL NORMS IN THE MINDS OF YOUNG PEOPLE	324
Ganiev Maksudjon Najimovich	
TALABALARDA PROKRASTINATSIYA DARAJASINI KAMAYTIRISH VA OLDINI OLISHNING NAZARIY TAHLILI	328
Ismailov Sanjarbek Sherzod o'g'li	
O'SMIRLARDA DEVIANT XULQ SHAKLLANISHINING OTA-ONA MUNOSABATLARI BILAN BOG'LIQLIGI	331
Mo'minova Dilrabo Murodillayevna	
O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA PSIXIK RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI	334
N.Z.Ismoilova, S.S.Berdiyeva, H.T.Baxriddinova	
ZO'RAVONLIKKA UCHRAGAN O'SMIRLAR ORASIDA COPING STRATEGIYALARINING SHAKLLANISHIGA IJTIMOYIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH OMILLARINING TA'SIRI	337
Nishanova Zamira Taskarayevna, Komilova Komila Inomjon qizi	
O'SMIRLARNI AGRESSIV XULQ-ATVOR FENOMENINI PSIXOLOGIK JIHATLARINI O'RGANISH.....	339
Norqulova Dildora Shavkat qizi	
OLIY TALIM PEDAGOGLARDA FRUSTRATSION TOLERANTLIKNI NAMOYON BOLISHINING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI	342
Nurmatov Nurhayot Nurziyot o'g'li	
TALABALAR O'ZINI O'ZI FAOLLASHTIRISHI MUAMMOSINING MAHALLIY MUHITDA TADQIQ ETILISHI	345
Qurbonboyev Azimbek Nazirboy o'g'li	
TALABALARDA TADQIQOTCHILIK QOBILYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI	348
Saidakbarova Nigora	
O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDA DEVIANT XULQNING SHAKLLANISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR	351
Sattarova Shahnoza Qo'chqarovna, Erkinjonova Raximaxon Baxtiyor qizi	
TALIM TASHKILOTLARIDA "WELL-BEING MANAGEMENT" TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH: IJTIMOIY-PSIXOLOGIK YONDASHUV DOIRASIDAGI TAHLIL	353
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Muminov Temurbek Uralbaevich	
GLOBALASHUV DAVRIDA O'SMIRLARNING HAYOTIDA PSIXOLOGIYANING AHAMIYATI	356
Xolmuratova Mahbuba Maxmudovna, Mannonov Hamid Xolmurod o'g'li, Isroilova Sevinch Sobirjon qizi	
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ КОПИНГ-СТРАТЕГИЙ ПЕДАГОГОВ В СТРЕССОВЫХ СИТУАЦИЯХ	359
Аскарова Гулрух Оринбасаровна, Халматова Мумтоза Зафаржон кизи	

ВЛИЯНИЕ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА НА МЕЖЛИЧНОСТНЫЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ	363
Лутфуллаева И.А.	
RIVOJLANGAN XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TA'LIM TIZIMIDA MAKTAB DIREKTORLARINING BOSHQARUV MADANIYATI.....	365
Abdulxayeva M.B.	
INNOVATSION TALIM TIZIMIDA TALABALARNI KREATIV TAFAKKURINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK DETERMINANTLARI.....	369
Masharipova Saida Rahimovna, Jiyanboeva Sadokat Shonazarovna	
FORMATION OF SOCIO-COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN STUDENTS THROUGH BILINGUISTICS BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH.....	372
Najmiddinova Gulnoza Odilovna	
O'QITISH JARAYONIDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING PSIXOLOGIK JIHATLARI.....	376
Safarova Dilnoza Kuchkarovna, Kasimova Dildora Xusanovna	
ZAMONAVIY SHAXS RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMOLARI	379
Saidakbarova Nigora Abduraxim qizi, Saydiraxmonova Durdona Abror qizi	
PEDAGOGLARDA KREATIVLIKNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK-PEDAGOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI	382
Sh.D.Ablakulov	
PSYCHOLOGICAL BASES OF POSITIVE PSYCHOLOGY AND POSITIVITY IN PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY	385
Shakhnoza Sattarova Kochkarovna	
PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PROFESSIONAL ADAPTATION	388
Shodiyeva Rayhon Saydullayevna	
YOSH VA PEDAGOGIK PSIXOLOGIYA: TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIDAGI MUAMMOLAR.....	391
Tuqboyeva Dilshoda Zaynievna, Saliddinova Nilufar Lochin qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON OLIY TA'LIM DASTURLARINI XALQARO AKKREDITATSIYADAN O'TKAZISH TAJRIBASI	393
Tursunov Tajimurad Mirsaidovich, Berdiqulov Ravshan Shavkatovich	
PEDAGOGIK DIAGNOSTIKA PEDAGOGIKANING ILMIY VA AMALIY SOHASI SIFATIDA	396
Umarova Malika Xisabidinovna, Xolboboyeva M.A.	
TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA LIDERLIK KOMPETENSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI.....	399
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Sobirova Shahlo Saminjonovna	
O'QUV MOTIVATSIYASI MUAMMOSI XORIJ PSIXOLOGIYASIDA TADQIQOTLAR PREDMETI SIFATIDA.....	402
D.Sh.Yuldashova	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В ОБУЧЕНИИ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ НАУК.....	405
Алиева Камола Саиднегматовна	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ КОГНИТИВНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ КАК ОСНОВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ НАУЧНОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА ПЕДАГОГА.....	408
Анварова Хуснора Давронбек кизи	
ЗНАЧЕНИЕ И РОЛЬ АРТ-ТЕРАПИИ В РАБОТЕ С ДЕТЬМИ.....	411
Асанова Гузаль Мухарамовна, Нуруллаев Адхамбек	
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ СОВЛАДАЮЩЕГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ У МОЛОДЕЖИ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ.....	414
Аскарова Гулрух Оринбасаровна	
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ ФРУСТРАЦИОННОЙ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ ПЕДАГОГОВ.....	418
Аскарова Гулрух Оринбасаровна, Рустамова Мубина Эркин кизи	

УМЕНИЯ ОРИЕНТИРОВАТЬСЯ В ТРУДОВОМ ЗАДАНИИ У УМСТВЕННО ОТСТАЛЫХ УЧАЩИХСЯ МЛАДШИХ КЛАССОВ.....	422
Зохидова К.Х.	
РОЛЬ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ В ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ СОПРОВОЖДЕНИИ И ВОСПИТАНИИ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ	424
М.М.Агзамова, Карпенко А.А.	
КОГНИТИВНЫЕ И ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ФАКТОРЫ МОТИВАЦИИ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА У МОЛОДЕЖИ НОВОГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ (ПОКОЛЕНИЯ Z И ПОКОЛЕНИЯ ALPHA).....	427
Мухамеджанова Р.Р.	
4-Sho'ba. Amaliy psixologiya: psixologik xizmat muammolari va innovatsion yechimlari.....	430
PEDAGOGIK JAMOALARDA PROJECT MANAGEMENT METODLARINING JAMOAVIY MOTIVATSIYAGA TA'SIRI.....	431
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Ashurov Muhammad Zokir o'g'li	
ИСТОРИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ ПОНЯТИЯ «ОДАРЕ́ННОСТЬ».....	433
Байбаева Мухайе Худайбергеновна, Зайниддинова Хилола Абдилвахоб кизи	
GLOBALASHUV JARAYONIDA HUQUQBUZARLIKLAR PSIXOPROFILAKTIKASI MUAMMOLARI	436
Qodirov Obid Safarovich, Utayev Umid Saidaloyevich	
TURLI AVLOD VAKILLARIDA KASBIY MOTIVATSIYA VA KASB TANLASH MEXANIZMLARINING PSIXOLOGIK TAHLILI	439
Jabborov Xazrat Xusenovich, Kamola Xodjaeva	
STRESS HAQIDA UMUMIY PSIXOLOGIK TUSHUNCHA	442
Aksakalova Nilufar Oybekovna	
XOTIN-QIZLARDA OILAVIY ZO'RAVONLIKDAN KEYINGI STRESS HOLATLARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISHNING IJTIMOY PSIXOLOGIK DETERMINANTLARI.....	446
Alimova Umida Raxmatillayevna	
BOJXONA TIZIMI XODIMLARIDA STRESSGA BARQARORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI	449
Fayzullayeva Xurshida Erkin qizi	
KASBIY O'ZINI ANGLASH VA O'ZINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MOTIVLARI.....	452
G.Andakulova	
VIRTUAL MULOQOT VA RAQAMLI IJTIMOY MUHITDA YOSHLARNING DEVIANT XULQ-ATVORI SHAKLLANISHINING PSIXOLOGIK MEXANIZMLARI	455
G'aniyev Maqsudjon Najim o'g'li, Nizomiddinova Feruza Faxriddin qizi, Bahriddinova Hulkaroy Tojiddinova	
RUHIY SALOMATLIKNI SAQLASHDA PSIXOLOGIK OMILLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	460
Hasanova Dilshoda Avazbek qizi	
IJTIMOY TARMOQLARNING SHAXS RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI.....	463
Ismoilova Dilso'z, Murodjonova Mavzuna Latifjon qizi, Tilapboyeva Rayxona Komiljon qizi	
TALABALARDAGI KOMMUNIKATIV VA IJTIMOY KOMPETENTLIK XUSUSIYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	466
Nazarova Malohat Axmedovna	
FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN STUDENTS WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENTS.....	469
Shakhnoza Pulatova	
O'SMIR YOSHIDAGI O'QUVCHILAR SAMARALI MULOQATDA O'QITUVCHILARNING KOMMUNIKATIV SIFATLARNI NAMOYON BO'LISHI	472
Xalmuratova Dilaram Abdikarimovna, Saydazimova Ziyoda Baxtiyor qizi, Nurmuhamedova Mohidil Nodir qizi	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASRIDA TA'LIM JARAYONINI BOSHQARISH INNOVATSIYALARI.....	475
Mamanazarova Nargiza Komildjanovna, Mirzayeva Shaxida Abdinabiyevna	

O'SPIRINLARNING IJTIMOYIY TARMOQLARDAGI MULOQOT MADANIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IJTIMOYIY-PSIXOLOGIK JIHATLARI.....	478
Salomov Shamsiddin Saboxiddin o'g'li, Yaxshiboyeva Ruxshona Husniddin qizi, Alimjonova Durdona Yunusjon qizi	
MOSLASHUVCHAN XULQ-ATVOR XUSUSIYATI, IFODALANISH MUAMMOLARI.....	482
Sh.B.Qurbanova	
KONCHILIK VA QAZIB OLISH SANOATI SOHASIDA PSIXOLOGIK SALOMATLIKNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH TIZIMI.....	487
Sh.U. Turobova	
SHAXS VAQTINI IDROK ETISH VA BOSHQARISHNING TO'RT USULI.....	491
Solayev Og'abek Ilhombek o'g'li	
AYBDORLIK HISSINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI: XORIY OLIMLARI TADQIQOTLARIDA YORITILISH.....	494
Sultanova Saida Muhiddin qizi	
EDUKOLOGIYA VA KOMMUNIKATSIYANING KESISHGAN NUQTALARI: METODOLOGIK QARASHLAR TAHLILI.....	496
To'g'onboeva Qizlarxon Ikromjon qizi, Ruzmetova Xilola Abdusharipovna	
ZAMONAVIY SHAXS RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOYIY-PSIXOLOGIK MUAMMOLAR.....	501
Tuqboeva Dilshoda Zaynievna, Mardonova Mardona Farhodovna	
CORRECTION OF ANXIETY IN CHILDREN.....	503
Umarova M.Kh., Sabirova N. I.	
PEDAGOGIK DIAGNOSTIKANING MAQSADI VA SHAXS RIVOJLANISHIDAGI O'RNI.....	505
Umarova Malika Xisabidinovna, Abdurasulova Ra'no Saloxiddinovna	
VIRTUAL MUZEYLAR VA ULARNING TARBIVAVIY IMKONIYATLARI.....	508
Voxidova N.X., Yusupova M. U.	
O'SMIR YOSHIDAGI O'QUVCHILAR SAMARALI MULOQATIDA O'QITUVCHILARNING KOMMUNIKATIV SIFATLARI NAMOYON BO'LISHI.....	510
Xalmuratova Dilaram Abdikarimovna, Saydazimova Ziyoda Baxtiyor qizi, Nurmuhammedova Mohidil Nodir qizi	
O'SMIRLARNING PUL HAQIDAGI IJTIMOYIY TASAVVURLARI SHAKLLANISHIDA ETNOPSIXOLOGIK QADRIYATLAR VA MADANIY IDENTIFIKATSIYA OMILLARINING O'ZARO TA'SIRI.....	512
Xolmuratova Mahbuba Maxmudovna	
INSON PSIXIKASI TASHQI MUHIT VA ICHKI HOLAT O'RTASIDAGI O'ZARO TA'SIR NATIJASIDA SHAKLLANISHI.....	515
Xolmurotova Mahbuba Mahmudovna, Ergashova Shaxinabonu Boboqulovna, Safarova Lobar Alisherovna	
ОТКЛАДЫВАНИЕ ДЕЛ КАК ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ЯВЛЕНИЕ: МЕХАНИЗМЫ И ПРИЧИНЫ ПРОКРАСТИНАЦИИ.....	518
Асанова Гузаль Мухарамовна, Ганибекова Ситора	
ДЕВИАНТНОЕ ПОВЕДЕНИЕ У ПОДРОСТКОВ.....	521
Аскарова Гулрух Оринбасаровна, Шапранова Милана Павловна	
МОТИВАЦИОННЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОСУЖДЕННЫХ К ТРУДОВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ И ОБУЧЕНИЮ В ПЕНИТЕНЦИАРНОЙ СИСТЕМЕ.....	525
М.А.Сайдуллаева	
5-Sho'ba. Shaxsning ruhiy salomatligi va salomatlik psixologiyasining dolzarb masalalari.....	529
O'SMIRLIK DAVRIDAGI BOLALARDA AGRESSIYANING NAMOYON BO'LISHI VA UNI BARTARAF ETISH USULLARI.....	530
Jalilova S.X., Aloyeva F., G'aybullaeva A.	
TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA HR-MENEJMENT TIZIMINI JORIY ETISHNING SAMARADORLIGI.....	533
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Bekmuratova Kamola Xasanovna	
BOLALARNI ZO'RAVONLIKDAN HIMOYA QILISH MEXANIZMLARI.....	535
Abbosova Uzrobonu Erkin qizi	

AUTIZM SPEKTRI BUZILISHI BO'LGAN MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA VIDEODELLASHTIRISHNING IJTIMOY KO'NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	538
<i>Atabayeva Dilrabo Ixtiyor qizi</i>	
GLOBAL O'ZGARISHLAR FONIDA KASBIY STRESS.....	543
<i>Bog'bekova Dilnoza Shonazarovna</i>	
GIPERTONIYA BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA STRESSNI BOSHQARISHNING PSIXOLOGIK MEXANIZMLARI	546
<i>Eshchanova Nasiba Matnazarovna</i>	
SHAXSNING RUHIY SALOMATLIGI VA SALOMATLIK PSIXOLOGIYASINING DOLZARB MASALALARI	549
<i>Inogamova Shaxzoda Raximovna</i>	
NEUROPROTECTIVE PROPERTIES OF PROPOFOL AND SEVOFLURAN: POSSIBILITIES OF PREVENTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF DYSFUNCTION IN COGNITIVE PROCESSES	553
<i>Karimova G. Kh., Khodjimurodova M. Yu.</i>	
YETUKLIK DAVRIDA INSULT TASHXISLI BEMORLAR BILAN PSIXOKORREKSION ISH OLIB BORISHNING DASTURIY ASOSLARI.....	556
<i>L.U.Atajanova</i>	
SHAXS RUHIY SALOMATLIGINING PSIXOLOGIK VA IJTIMOY DETERMINANTLARI.....	558
<i>N.A.Saidakbarova, Karimova Gulnoza</i>	
GIPERTONIYA KASALLIGIDA BEMORLARDA NARKOZDAN SO'NG XOTIRANI O'ZGARISHI.....	561
<i>Karimova Gulchehra Xamidullayevna, Axmatova Diyora Donyor qizi, Ulug'babayeva Soliha G'ayratjon qizi</i>	
ZO'RAVONLIKKA UCHRAGAN AYOLLAR BILAN PSIXOLOGIK MASLAHAT TASHKIL ETISH TAMOYILLARI.....	564
<i>Nazarova Muharram Yunus qizi</i>	
SHAXS RIVOJLANISHI VA SALOMATLIGINI ASRASHDA IJTIMOY TARMOQLARNING O'RNI.....	567
<i>O.M. Zaripov</i>	
BULLING VA ZO'RAVONLIK HOLATLARINING PSIXOLOGIK, IJTIMOY VA PEDAGOGIK OMILLARI.....	569
<i>Qarshiyeva Dilafuz, Sattorova Mohinur Sherali qizi</i>	
MAHALLIY NARKOZ PAYTIDA TAFAKKURNING YO'QOLMASLIGI.....	572
<i>Karimova Gulchehra Xamidullayevna, Nizomova Munisa Amriddinova, Raximova Shaxnoza Ravshanovna</i>	
SHAXSNING RUHIY SALOMATLIGI VA SALOMATLIK PSIXOLOGIYASINING DOLZARB MASALALARI	575
<i>Pulatova Gulnoza Murodilovna, Umrzaqova Gulzoda Abdurahmon qizi</i>	
NEVROTIK BEMORLARDA XISSIY O'ZGARISHLAR	578
<i>Karimova Gulchehra Xamidullayevna, Ostonayeva Novbaxor Mamaraimovna, Inomova Odina Abdulvohid qizi</i>	
COVID-19 PANDEMIYASINING INSON RUHIYATIGA TA'RISI.....	581
<i>Qadirova Shahnoza Saidabdullayevna</i>	
NARKOZDAN SO'NG BEMORLARDA XOTIRANI TIKLANISHI.....	584
<i>Karimova Gulchehra Xamidullayevna, Shukurova Nigora Quدراتila qizi</i>	
NUTQIDA KAMCHILIGI BO'LGAN BOLALAR BILAN OLIB BORILADIGAN PSIXOKORREKSION ISHLAR TIZIMI	587
<i>S.A.Mamatisayeva</i>	
OPERATSIYADAN SO'NG SEZGI JARAYONLARINING TIKLANISHI.....	590
<i>Karimova Gulchehra Xamidullayevna, Tojiyeva Go'zal Karimjonovna, Ollamova Nargiza Hamdam qizi</i>	
TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA BOSHQARUV TIZIMINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA “DIGITAL TWIN” (RAQAMLI EGIZAK) TEXNOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA MODELLASHTIRISHNING ILMIY-AMALIY ASOSLARI.....	593
<i>Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Gaymnazarov Odiljon Kurbanovich</i>	

BOLALIKDAGI PSIXOLOGIK JAROHATLARNING O‘SMIR SHAXSIY IDENTIFIKATSIYASI SHAKLLANISHIGA TA‘SIRI: RETROSPEKTIV TAHLIL ASOSIDAGI YONDASHUV.....	596
<i>Xudayberganova Roziya Nurniyazovna</i>	
BOLALARDA NARKOZDAN SO‘NG SEZGINI YUQORI BO‘LISHI	599
<i>Karimova Gulchehra Xamidullayevna, Zakirova Sadoqat Kudayberganovna, Yangiboyev Zokir Tohir o‘g‘li</i>	
НЕВРОЗЫ У ДЕТЕЙ: ПРИЧИНЫ И СИМПТОМЫ.....	602
<i>Абдурахимов Дониёр Абдусаидович</i>	
INVESTIGATION OF THE RECOVERY OF COGNITIVE PROCESSES AND MEMORY FUNCTIONS AFTER GENERAL ANESTHESIA THROUGH NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL MEASUREMENTS.....	605
<i>Karimova Gulchexra Khamidullayevna</i>	
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ СОПРОВОЖДЕНИЕ И ПОВЫШЕНИЕ КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ СЕМЬИ В УСЛОВИЯХ БОЛЕЗНИ РЕБЁНКА.....	608
<i>Асанова Гузаль Мухарамовна</i>	
NARKOZDAN SO‘NG UYQU BUZILISHLARI	612
<i>Karimova Gulchexra Xamidullayevna, Kilichova Gulnoza Bobomurotova, Xalikova Shaxzoda Radjabovna</i>	
ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ДЕТСКОГО АУТИЗМА: ФАКТОРЫ, ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ, ПРОБЛЕМЫ.....	616
<i>Асрарханова Эътибор Абдувахаб қизи</i>	
БЕССОННИЦА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ЦИФРОВЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ (с включением проекта «Веб-приложение для людей, страдающих бессонницей»).....	620
<i>Туракулова И. Х., Делеверханов С. А.</i>	
ILK O‘SPIRINLARDA STRESSNI KELITIRIB CHIQRUVCHI OMILLAR HAQIDAGI TASAVVURLARNING O‘ZIGA XOSLIGI	623
<i>N.Z. Ismoilova</i>	
STRESSGA BARDOSHLILIK – SHAXS RUHIY SALOMATLIGINING ASOSI SIFATIDA	626
<i>Ruzmatova Nigina Shotilla qizi</i>	
O‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA XULQIY OG‘ISHLARNI KORREKSIYALASH USULLARI.....	629
<i>To‘raboyev Azamat Muxamadullayevich</i>	
SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO THE FORMATION OF STRESS RESISTANCE	632
<i>Tuychiyeva Shakhlo Shavkatovna</i>	
TALABALARDA RUHIY SALOMATLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASHDA STRESSGA BARDOSHLILIK VA EMOTSIONAL INTELLEKTNING ROLI.....	634
<i>Xajiyeva Iroda Adambayevna</i>	
MASS-MEDIANI TA‘SIRI OSTIDAGI O‘Z JONIGA QASD QILISH: VERTER SINDROMI PSIXOLOGIYASI TAHLILI.....	637
<i>Xudoyberganova Sharofat G‘ofurjon qizi</i>	
NERV KASALLIKLARDA BEMORLARDA HISSIY O‘ZGARISHLARI.....	641
<i>Xujamova Ruhshona G‘olib qizi</i>	
СУИЦИДАЛЬНОЕ ПОВЕДЕНИЕ У ДЕВУШЕК-ПОДРОСТКОВ.....	643
<i>Аскарова Гулрух Оринбасаровна, Абдуллина Аделина Маратовна</i>	
СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ И ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В СУДЕБНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ЭКСПЕРТИЗЕ	647
<i>Мухтарова Азиза Эркиновна</i>	
INTROVERT VA EKSTROVERT SHAXSLARNING INGLIZ TILINI O‘ZLASHTIRISHDAGI PSIXOLOGIK FARQLARI.....	650
<i>Konratbaeva Ayjamal Bazarbaevna, Ochilova Xurshida Bahromovna</i>	
BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFLAR O‘QUVCHILARINING TANQIDIY TAFAKKURINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK MEKANIZMLARI	652
<i>Konratbaeva Ayjamal Bazarbaevna, Yusupova Xursanoy Fazliddin qizi</i>	
МЕНЕДЖМЕНТ ИММЕРСИВНОЙ ИНКЛЮЗИВНОЙ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СРЕДЫ	655
<i>Оманова Гулноза Абдиназаровна</i>	

KO'P MILLATLI TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA YETAKCHILIK USLUBLARINING ETNOPSIXOLOGIK JIHATLARI	658
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, G'ayratova Malohat O'tkir qizi	
TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONIDA BIXEVIORIAL MENEJMENT NAZARIYASINING MOHIYATI.....	660
Umarova Navbahor Shokirovna, Sangirova Nargiza Yuldashevna	

CORRECTION OF ANXIETY IN CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the issues of educating the younger generation in today’s rapidly changing, highly intense, and complex era of globalization. It focuses on protecting young people from moral threats that contradict universal values, fostering their development into highly spiritual individuals, and addressing one of the most urgent tasks—planning and organizing educational activities in educational institutions. The article also analyzes the successful socialization of the individual and the formation of moral and ethical qualities.

Key words: era of globalization, youth education, morality, pedagogical influence, children’s anxiety, individual-psychological characteristics, nonverbal communication.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola jadal sur’atlar bilan o’zgarib borayotgan bugungi o’ta shiddatli va murakkab globallashuv davrida yoshlarni tarbiyalash masalalariga bag’ishlanadi. Ularni umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga zid bo’lgan ma’naviy xurujlardan asrash, yuksak ma’naviyatli shaxs sifatida kamol toptirish, shuningdek, ta’lim muassasalarida o’quvchi-yoshlar bilan uyushtiriladigan tarbiyaviy tadbirlarni rejalashtirish va tashkil etish eng dolzarb masalalardan biridir. Shaxsning muvaffaqiyatli ijtimoiylashuvi, unda ma’naviy-axloqiy fazilatlarni shakllantirish masalalari ham maqola doirasida tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so’zlar: globallashuv davri, yoshlar tarbiyasi, axloq, pedagogik ta’sir, bolalar bezovtaligi, individual-psixologik xususiyatlar, noverbal kommunikatsiya.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена вопросам воспитания молодежи в эпоху стремительных и сложных процессов глобализации. Актуальными задачами являются защита молодых людей от духовных угроз, противоречащих общечеловеческим ценностям, их развитие как высоконравственных личностей, а также организация и планирование воспитательных мероприятий в образовательных учреждениях. Особое внимание уделяется вопросам формирования у личности морально-нравственных качеств и успешной социализации.

Ключевые слова: эпоха глобализации, воспитание молодежи, нравственность, педагогическое воздействие, детская тревожность, индивидуально-психологические особенности, невербальная коммуникация.

In today’s rapidly changing and complex period of globalization, the education of young people, their protection from spiritual aggression that contradicts universal values, and their formation as highly moral individuals are among the most pressing issues.

In the upbringing of a well-rounded personality, the formation of socially and professionally necessary qualities plays a significant role. Since ancient times, our people have attached great importance to the cultivation of good morals, and morally upright individuals have always been highly respected. The development of social and professional qualities in a person occurs during social activity, in which the individual’s transformation—formation and development—progresses rapidly. The subject of the educational process strives to internalize the pedagogical influence directed toward them. Therefore, adopting a comprehensive approach to planning and organizing educational activities with students, as well as effectively using pedagogical and educational technologies aimed at developing the learner’s personality, has become a requirement of our time.

The successful socialization of an individual depends on the formation of moral and ethical qualities, and in pedagogy, it is important to be able to “measure” the development of these qualities through specific methods. For the systematic implementation of the educational process, teachers must diagnose all changes occurring in the learner’s personality. Purposeful pedagogical influence on the formation and development of moral-ethical qualities ensures the achievement of planned outcomes.

Undoubtedly, behavioral reactions to life situations are often rooted in previously formed incorrect responses due to improper upbringing. Situations that provoke difficulties, anxiety, and irritation in tense communication settings will inevitably manifest in the future [1.45].

Children’s anxiety is a direct consequence of the high pressure present in modern life. Its symptoms are gradually increasing worldwide. If twenty years ago only a quarter of the population in developed countries experienced mild anxiety, by the end of the millennium this figure had risen to three-quarters. Anxiety arises from constant worry, insecurity, and the expectation of negative outcomes—it is the result of a persistent sense of unease. Living in such a state is difficult for a person: it drains energy, weakens willpower, disturbs consciousness, and leads to impulsive, unconsidered actions. Anxiety is an early sign of future distress. Excessive anxiety is at the root of many behavioral problems among schoolchildren. Persistent feelings of fear and misunderstanding suppress willpower, hinder rational thinking, and provoke rash actions.

Anxiety and worry differ from each other: worry is a vague feeling of unease caused by an uncertain sense of danger or fear. Unlike worry, anxiety has more concrete personal and emotional characteristics. An anxious person is insecure, distrustful of their own decisions and actions, tends to anticipate unpleasant outcomes, and is emotionally unstable.

Causes of anxiety in children:

Common childhood fears include thunderstorms, darkness, wild animals, heights, being late for school, or being called to the blackboard. These fears are situational and usually harmless. However, in some children, such fears leave deep emotional traces. Children’s anxiety often arises in the following circumstances:

Imposing demands that do not match the child’s abilities;

Making demands that place the child in an uncomfortable or humiliating position;

Excessive leniency, indifference, or neglect by adults, leading to a sense of danger and insecurity.

Anxiety has a hereditary basis, but the external environment can either reduce or intensify its development. Between ages 10 and 12, the presence or absence of anxiety becomes a stable personality trait. A child’s tendency to easily fall into an anxious state—whether innate or acquired—shapes their behavior.

Common causes of children’s anxiety [2.52]:

- Constitutional features of the nervous system;
- Conditions associated with fear and repeated failure;
- Illness or its consequences;
- Threats or intimidation from adults;
- Excessive imagination;
- Activation of self-defense instincts;
- Consequences of overly restrictive upbringing;
- Feelings of guilt over failure to meet the standards of other children.

One of the most challenging tasks for an educator is diagnosing the individual-psychological characteristics of a student through signals obtained via nonverbal communication channels. Successfully addressing this task helps the teacher maintain effective “feedback” during the educational process and evaluate the results of pedagogical influence.

During individualized pedagogical correction with a student, the use of explanatory conversation techniques may include the following stages:

The method of active listening.

Listening plays an essential role both in diagnosis and in correction. The educator should pay attention not only to the student’s words but also to the meanings they convey, the emotional tone of sentences, and the external manifestations of inner feelings expressed during conversation [3.69].

A student may postpone discussing certain issues until they feel sufficiently comfortable. Once they become fully engaged in communication, the teacher should consider not only verbal messages but also nonverbal cues—facial expressions, gestures, posture, tone, and modulation of voice [3.71].

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